

IMPROVING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND TACTICAL-TECHNICAL TRAINING OF KURASH WRESTLERS

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Annotation: The article discusses psychological and tactical-technical issues in the preparation of kurash wrestlers. It has been proven that improvement of the tactical, technical and psychological training of kurash wrestlers is required, the main problems in this process have been identified, and the feasibility of their use has been proven to quickly make optimal technical and tactical decisions in conditions of competitive activity.

Key words: wrestlers, kurash wrestling, methodology, tactical and technical solution, psychological preparation, competitive activity.

Introduction. Improving the methods of technical, tactical and psychological training of kurash wrestlers helps to improve the results of competitive activity and sportsmanship [4, 6, 7]. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is modern publications of leading scientists involved in the theory and methodology of physical culture and sports [1, 2]. However, the problems of improving the training of kurash wrestlers, taking into account modern requirements of competitive activity and the search for means and methods of forming an effective arsenal of competitive variable technical and tactical actions of wrestlers, have not been sufficiently considered in modern scientific publications [3, 5].

Currently, there is a high level of competition in the competitive activities of kurash wrestlers. Many researchers note that in modern elite sports it is impossible to achieve high sports results only by increasing the volume and intensity of training loads, therefore, the search for reserves for further improving sportsmanship is of

particular relevance [8, 9, 11, 12]. An integrated psychological and pedagogical approach to optimizing the mental states of athletes can become such a reserve. According to the results of many studies, emotional states have a direct impact on the performance of an athlete [10, 13]. An athlete must control himself, his actions, experiences, feelings, actions, and be able to regulate his behavior in extreme conditions. However, scientific publications devoted to improving the psychological training of kurash wrestlers are clearly not enough.

Techniques and tactics in kurash wrestling are extremely diverse, and their diversity is constantly growing [14, 15, 17]. The development of kurash wrestling techniques and tactics is due to unrelenting sports competition in the international arena and changes in competition rules. At the same time, as our survey showed, many leading experts in kurash wrestling, technique in combination with tactics is the basis of a wrestler's sportsmanship, while other aspects of training play a supporting role in relation to this resulting component of activity [16, 18]. Improvement of technical and tactical training of kurash wrestlers is required.

The essence of wrestling psychology is the motivation to achieve success, the desire to be first in competition with equals. Achieving victory requires the athlete to maximize the mobilization of his physical and mental capabilities both in the process of preparing for competitions and directly in competitions. Modern sport is characterized by exceptional density of results and extreme mobilization of participants [19, 20].

With the same qualifications, level of development of physical qualities, technical and tactical training, an athlete with a high level of mental readiness and corresponding personality indicators has an advantage. Therefore, improving the psychological training of kurash wrestlers is an urgent problem in sports science. During training, one has to deal with the diagnosis of the labile, rapidly changing state of wrestlers. In order to increase the effectiveness of training and competitive activities, it is necessary, to a certain degree of probability, to diagnose the current mental state as a state of mental readiness or unpreparedness to perform a specific

exercise [21]. Diagnosis of a mental state involves the use of techniques that allow repetition when working with the same person. Practice and special research have allowed us to divide all known methods of managing mental states into several groups:

- physical;
- psychotherapeutic;
- psychological;
- pedagogical.

An analysis of works on the use of psychological and pedagogical methods for regulating mental state shows that the effectiveness of most of them was tested before the start. At the same time, the results of an analytical review of specialized literature convincingly show that mental tension in athletes appears long before competitions, and this premature activation has a strong negative impact on the pre-start state and on the effectiveness of competitive activity.

An important direction in the system of psychological training of athletes is the development of the ability to self-regulate mental processes and emotional state. A wrestler's independent training, display of self-discipline, and use of self-regulation methods to calm down and tune in to fights allows young wrestlers to master the ability to independently regulate their mental processes and emotional state.

The goals of psychophysical regulation in sports are:

- understanding the direct influence of a moral person on the stability of the neuropsychic sphere and the health status of a young wrestler;
- the athlete's awareness of the psychological characteristics and patterns of formation of his own main mental states;
- development of the necessary mental hygiene skills, rational habits, character traits and personality traits;
- mastering techniques for active self-regulation of one's vitality, level of performance and creative capabilities;

- understanding of the psychological mechanisms of correction and self-correction of one's mental states.

To characterize the psychophysical tone of a young wrestler, indicators such as the amount of energy expended by the body in response and mobilized in response to influencing disturbance are taken into account, as well as the breathing pattern and the degree of relaxation of skeletal muscles.

The research results allow us to conclude that psychoregulatory training and neurolinguistic programming can significantly increase a young wrestler's tolerance to stress overload. The main task of self-regulation is to ensure the adequacy and efficiency of behavioral reactions, that is, the proper adaptive effectiveness of the psychophysical actions of a young wrestler as a whole. Outstanding achievements in sports, as a rule, are born first in the mental sphere of the athlete and only then are realized in the sports arena. At the moment of establishing the highest sporting achievements, the athlete seems to be inside himself, in a state of trance, self-confident, completely calm and completely alienated from society.

At each stage of psychological preparation of athletes, certain problems arise, so it is advisable to think through and organize stage-by-stage psychological preparation depending on the tasks facing athletes at different periods. Thus, at the initial stage, it is necessary to update and motivate psychological work, to create interest among athletes in working on themselves. In initial training groups, the trainer is faced with the problem of maintaining attention on a specific object for a long time. Creating interest in itself promotes concentration. Subordination of attention, its selective content is the first step in the conscious work of the brain. Learning to voluntarily control your attention is the beginning of self-control, increasing work efficiency and quickly achieving your goal. Special exercises are carried out in individual and group forms through game activities, systematically, with gradually increasing complexity and in close connection with the tasks of technical and physical training at each specific stage.

Psychotechnical games, autogenic training, and psychoregulatory training are used. For wrestlers, kinesthetic sensitivity is important - a sense of balance, interaction with a partner, "feeling the mat". Functional training still plays an important role, but winning a fight can be largely influenced by sensitivity, agility, reaction speed, and the ability to use the enemy's energy. Therefore, it is advisable to begin the development of kinesthetic sensitivity from the initial stages of preparation. In addition to purely sports methods, it is recommended to include in the training group psychological training and game moments, with the help of which the effects of liberation from the fear of contacts with other people, from internal pressures and excessive tension are achieved, finding a soft, energetically beneficial way of interaction, creating a friendly emotional background for the group.

Conclusions. 1. The use of training methods aimed at quickly making optimal technical and tactical decisions in conditions of competitive activity significantly improves sports results and develops the mental abilities of kurash wrestlers. When mastering the technical elements of free wrestling and the basic actions of wrestlers, a private teaching methodology, consisting of a system of tasks, objectives and methodological instructions, which is based on the implementation of special exercises, elements, phases, parts of the technique and their combination actions as a whole, becomes important. optimal conditions are created for the correct assimilation of the basic actions of kurash wrestling. The basic elements of kurash wrestling are the main positions of the wrestlers in the standing position, the distance between opponents, methods of movement, directions of maneuvering, gripping, stops, jerks and releases from them, performing a basic technique, defense and counter-reception, the use of tactical preparations, combinations.

2. Successful formation of the motor function of kurash wrestlers largely depends on the method of teaching the elements of wrestling. The choice of methods and teaching techniques is determined by the specific pedagogical task, the specifics of the content of the educational material, the age and level of preparedness of the kurash wrestlers. Based on the form of management of the educational process and

direct communication between the coach and young kurash wrestlers, one can distinguish methods of ensuring visibility and methods of using words. To master the profiling elements of wrestling and basic actions, the exercise method is used. The choice and application of the optimal method by the coach significantly accelerates the process of learning technique and tactics by young wrestlers in the conditions of the dynamic development of kurash wrestling, and helps to improve the effectiveness of competitive activity.

References:

1. Алляров, И. К. (2023). Волейбол как основа физического воспитания студентов в высших учебных заведениях. *Экономика и социум*, (10 (113)-1), 377-380.
2. Акимов, Н. Т., & Казакбаев, А. М. (2023). Основные методы преподавания гимнастики в высших учебных заведениях. *Экономика и социум*, (10 (113)-2), 461-464.
3. Алляров, С. К., Казакбаев, А. М., & Казакбаев, Б. М. (2023). Волейбол как средство сохранения и укрепления физического здоровья студентов высших учебных заведений. *Экономика и социум*, (1-2 (104)), 152-155.
4. Казакбаев, Б. М., Казакбаев, А. М., & Алляров, И. К. (2022). Сила как физическое качество спортсменов. *Экономика и социум*, (6-2 (97)), 456-459.
5. Казакбаев, А. М., Абдикамалов, Х. И., & Курбаниязов, Ж. С. (2020). К вопросу о правильном питании спортсменов. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5 (59)), 214-217.
6. Казакбаев, А., & Мамутов, А. (2021). Преподавание волейбола в системе физического воспитания общеобразовательной школы.
7. Казакбаев, Б. М., Казакбаев, А. М., & Алляров, И. К. (2022). *Мировая наука. Мировая наука Учредители: ООО" Институт управления и социально-экономического развития"*, (6), 91-94.

8. Казакбаев, А. М., & Аллаяров, И. К. (2022). Выносливость как физическое качество спортсменов. Теория и практика современной науки, (6 (84)), 128-131.
9. Казакбаев, А. М., Абдикамалов, Х. И., & Курбаниязов, Ж. С. (2016). Традиции и ритуалы Олимпийских игр. *Ученый XXI века*, (6-2 (19)), 23-25.
10. Казакбаев, А., & Мамутов, А. (2021). Преподавание волейбола в системе физического воспитания общеобразовательной школы.
11. Курбаниязов, Ж. С., Казакбаев, А. М., & Абдикамалов, Х. И. (2017). Изящный вид спорта-гольф. Теория и практика современной науки, (6 (24)), 464-467.
12. Курбаниязов, Ж. С., Казакбаев, А. М., & Абдикамалов, Х. И. (2018). Значение физической культуры в воспитании подрастающего поколения. Теория и практика современной науки, (6 (36)), 375-378.
13. Курбаниязов, Ж. С., Казахбаев, А. М., & Абдикамалов, Х. И. (2015). Использование каракалпакских народных игр как духовное наследие в процессе непрерывного образования. Апробация, (10), 52-54.
14. Табынбаев, А., Казакбаев, А., & Мамутов, А. (2021). Преподавание волейбола в системе физического воспитания общеобразовательной школы. Теория и практика современной науки, (6 (72)), 295-297.
15. Халеков, Р. М., & Каниязов, С. Ж. (2023). Взаимосвязь технико-тактической и психологической подготовки борцов. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (106)), 735-738.
16. Алхамов, А. Р., & Каниязов, С. Ж. (2023). Методика организации и подготовки борьбы на поясах. *Экономика и социум*, (5-2 (108)), 559-561.
17. Tengelbaevich, A. N. (2023). Health-improving physical culture as the basis for a healthy lifestyle of students in higher educational institutions. *Journal of Modern Educational Achievements*, 1212(12), 376-380.

18. Kazakbayev, A. M., Mamutov, A. B., & Koschanov, A. E. (2024). Features of individualization of athletes in sports games. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 2(4), 242-248.

19. Akimov, N. T., & Kazakbayev, A. M. (2024). Training students in gymnastic exercises in sportsmanship groups. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 2(4), 249-256.

20. Joldasbaevich, Q. S., & Rustamovich, A. A. (2023). Development of physical activities of students and youth through active and passive tourism. *Journal of education, ethics and value*, 2(10), 83-85.

21. Joldasbaevich, Q. S. (2024). The History of the Development of Judo and Sambo Wrestling. *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*, 4(4), 336-339.